

Disruptive Innovation for Sustainable Development in Nigeria

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Abstract

Disruptive innovation has emerged as a pivotal force in transforming economies globally, and Nigeria is no exception. This study explores the potential of disruptive technologies to drive sustainable development in Nigeria, focusing on sectors such as agriculture, healthcare, education, and financial services. As Nigeria grapples with challenges like poverty, unemployment, and inadequate infrastructure, disruptive innovations offer unique solutions that can enhance productivity, increase access to services, and foster economic growth. By leveraging technologies such as mobile applications, artificial intelligence (AI), and blockchain, Nigeria can create new market opportunities and improve existing processes. This research employs a mixed-methods strategy using both quantitative data analysis and qualitative input from relevant stakeholders in the business sector industry stakeholders to evaluate the effects of disruptive innovation on sustainable development goals (SDGs). Findings indicate that while disruptive technologies hold significant promise for enhancing economic resilience and social equity, their successful implementation requires a supportive regulatory framework, investment in digital skills, and Partnerships among the governmental and private enterprises. The study concludes with recommendations for policymakers to create an enabling environment that encourages innovation while addressing the socio-economic disparities prevalent in Nigerian society. This abstract summarizes the focus of the research while highlighting the relevance of disruptive innovation to Nigeria's sustainable development efforts.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence (AI), Human Development Index (HDI), Social Media Network, Internet Usage, Technology

Introduction

Creating a unique brand that survives over the years in today's dynamic business world typically needs more than just figuring out where you fit in the market. It includes identifying wholly new ways to produce profitability. To help you get started on your journey to disruptive innovation in 2020s, we've reviewed a list of companies who are transforming their industry.

As a means of breaking into an industry, disruptive innovation sees less lucrative areas as entry points. Then, by constant through innovation and development, these enterprises may obtain profitability in a competitive market. With superior products and services and a deep knowledge of customer experience, the business can outcompete and replace established brands.

Disruptive innovation has been a key focus of concern in both academic and business organizations. It refers to a product or approach that redefines competitiveness by supplying crucial traits for new market segments that are often overlooked by mainstream markets (Cruz-Sanchez et al., 2020).

These organisations have drastically transformed their industries, delivering important insights on how to correctly position your brand or company for ongoing success. By assessing these disruptive innovation organisations, you may gain inspiration and strategic guidance to advance your brand toward innovation and market dominance. This form of innovation necessitates that firms recognise and grab opportunities arising from increasing marketplaces and technologies within unforeseen contexts. Notably, the hypothesis of disruptive innovation can be combined with other concepts to provide new insights.

Disruptive innovation simplifies and decreases the cost of products and services for underserved markets. This enables smaller or new organizations to appeal to these people with simpler, lower affordable solutions, while established corporations frequently concentrate on improving their products for their wealthy customer base. For instance, Flavin (2021) integrates Foucault's concept of the episteme with disruptive innovation theory to analyze innovation in technology-enhanced learning. This novel approach suggests the emergence of a neoliberal episteme where technology itself is central.

Additionally, Lin et al. (2018) explore how knowledge assets foster disruptive innovation. They find that the embeddedness and originality of knowledge play distinct roles in outward-oriented versus internal-oriented disruptive innovations. Internet connectivity is a fantastic example of a disruptive technology because it altered various areas. Sustainable growth means progressively cultivating new ideas to challenge and potentially replace established market leaders over time.

Disruptive innovation is increasingly recognized as a pivotal force in shaping the digital economy, particularly in emerging markets like Nigeria. This introduction explores the landscape of Nigeria's digital economy, highlighting the transformative potential of technology to drive economic growth, enhance productivity, and foster innovative technology across various sectors. The use of disruptive financial technologies, such as Fintechs, is essential for achieving financial inclusion objectives at desired levels and speed (Ezeocha, 2024).

Effective strategies in promoting financial inclusion through digital driven technology in Nigeria include capping cash withdrawals, enforcing penalties for exceeding thresholds, and promoting digital adoption among individuals, companies, and bank account holders. However, forced inclusion may only benefit those with bank accounts rather than the unbanked population, leading to more financial data inclusion than financial inclusion. Challenges

include the uneven distribution of financial inclusion across gender, youth, education, income, and urban-rural areas (Lawal & Williams, 2023).

In summary, it fosters progress, stimulates competition, and facilitates the creation of new solutions to meet evolving customer demands. It has the capacity to disrupt industries, open up new market opportunities, and question present ways. By generating revolutionary items, services, or business models, disruptive innovation may raise efficiency, expand accessibility, and elevate client experiences. Its impact extends across various industries, from manufacturing to hospitality and tourism (Adeyinka-Ojo & Abdullah, 2019).

Statements of problems

Nigeria faces significant challenges in achieving sustainable development across various sectors, particularly in aligning linked with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) While efforts have been made to implement SDGs, full domestication remains unachieved (Benjamin et al., 2024). The country struggles with issues such as inadequate technological knowledge, insufficient funding, and lack of proper e-learning and ICT facilities in universities (Ofor-Douglas, 2023). These challenges impede progress in areas crucial for sustainable development, such as innovation, infrastructure, and quality education.

The successful adoption of disruptive innovation hinges on the availability of a digitally literate workforce. In Nigeria, there is a significant gap in digital skills, which hampers the ability of businesses to leverage new technologies effectively. This skills deficit may limit digital entrepreneurial and economic growth, as many potential entrepreneurs lack the necessary training to navigate the digital landscape.

A comprehensive approach involving policy reform, investment in digital skills, and infrastructure development into Nigeria's development strategy is essential for addressing existing challenges while aligning with the sustainable development goal 1 (poverty) and 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure). By fostering an environment conducive to innovation, Nigeria can harness its potential sustainable development that supports all societal groups. This strategy not only tackles current socio-economic difficulties but also ensures long-term sustainability for future generations.

Conceptual Framework

Fig. 1: The Conceptual Framework of Disruptive Innovation for Sustainable Development in Nigeria
Source: Author

Research Objective

The objective of this study is to specifically,

- i. investigate how disruptive innovations can be utilized to address key developmental challenges in Nigeria, such as healthcare access, education, and infrastructure deficits.
- ii. how technological innovations potential can impact improvement of livelihood through local communities while promoting sustainable economic growth.

Research Questions

These questions aim to provide a comprehensive exploration of the various facets of disruptive innovation's influence on sustainable economic growth:

1. How can the integration of disruptive innovations in divers' sectors contribute to economic growth and job creation in Nigeria.
2. In what ways can smart city technologies enhance urban planning to support better access and delivery of sustainable economic growth.

Hypotheses

H₀: There is no significant positive relationship between disruptive innovation explanatory variables (Social Media Network, POS, Internet Usage, Mobile and Web pay) and Human Development Index (HDI).

H₁: There is a significant positive relationship between disruptive innovation explanatory variables (Social Media Network, POS, Internet Usage, Mobile and Web pay) and Human Development Index (HDI).

Review of Related Literature:

Conceptual Review

Disruptive Innovation (Criterion Variable)

Disruptive innovation involves creating new markets or value networks by making products or services more affordable and accessible to a wider audience. Unlike Sustaining innovations, which improve current items for present customers, and disruptive innovations usually begin

at the lower end of the market or target neglected segments. While many studies highlight the benefits of disruptive innovation, some also discuss its contradictions and challenges. For example, Ibidunni et al. (2021) emphasize that disruptive initiatives should align with financial goals, social value, and customer benefits.

Grasping the concept of disruptive innovation is crucial for businesses to effectively manage evolving market conditions. By identifying opportunities for disruption and adjusting their strategies, companies can either capitalize on these innovations or protect themselves from potential threats. Adeniyi et al. (2021) points out the often strained relationship between universities and industries in product development, suggesting a possible lack of collaboration that could hinder innovation.

It's intriguing to note the contradictions in the literature about the origins of disruptive innovations. While some believe that disruptive innovations don't come from existing customers, a study by Preißner et al. (2023) found that 43% of the disruptive innovations sampled were actually developed by users. This challenges the conventional perspective and indicates that the sources of disruptive threats can vary based on factors like environmental turbulence and the type of innovation.

In conclusion, disruptive innovation is a complex phenomenon that requires firms to possess dynamic capabilities to identify and exploit opportunities in volatile environments (Cruz-Sanchez et al., 2020).

Social Media Networking

Social media networking involves using online platforms to connect, communicate, and share content with others. It has become a crucial part of modern communication and interaction for

both individuals and organizations. The impact of social media extends beyond personal use, affecting various industries. For instance, the tourist business employs online communities as a new advertising and marketing tool to target people (Kavoura & Kefallonitis, 2019).

Social networks have revolutionized interactions by eliminating geographical barriers and enabling real-time communication. While social media provides many advantages, it also comes with challenges. For instance, it supports relationship building, maintenance, and access to social resources (Mcewan, 2020).

Social networks have revolutionized interactions by removing geographical barriers and enabling real-time communication. They are also essential for businesses' marketing strategies, helping them reach broader audiences through targeted ads and influencer collaborations.

Absolutely! Social media networking is indeed a powerful tool that enhances personal connections, fosters professional growth, and boosts business marketing efforts in our digital era. It bridges distances, facilitates real-time communication, and provides platforms for targeted advertising and influencer partnerships, making it indispensable in today's interconnected world.

Point of Sales (POS) System

Point of Sale system is an essential tool for modern retail operations, combining hardware and software to facilitate efficient transaction processing while providing valuable insights into business performance. As technology continues to evolve, so too do the capabilities of POS systems, making them integral to both retail and hospitality industries.

A POS system functions as the key centre for executing sales transactions. It can be a physical device in a store or a virtual interface for online sales. Point of Sale (POS) systems have

witnessed tremendous transformation, shifting from simple cash registers to sophisticated digital platforms that support various retail processes. These systems now record sales, manage inventory, print invoices, calculate profits, and improve overall business services (Dewi et al., 2021).

POS applications have moved beyond just retail environments. In the food and beverage sector, mobile POS systems on iOS platforms have been created to assist restaurant owners in reviewing sales, assessing menus, and enhancing security by minimizing errors and fraud (Widjaja et al., 2021).

In conclusion, POS systems have become integral to modern retail operations, offering benefits such as improved productivity, enhanced merchandise control, and better customer service.

Web/Mobile Pay

Web Pay is a service that allows individuals and businesses to make payments directly from their bank accounts. For example, in California, the Franchise Tax Board offers Web Pay for paying state taxes or fees using checking or savings accounts. This service is free and provides options to view, cancel, or schedule future payments through an online account. Another novel approach is the use of blockchain technology to address issues such as single point of failure, transparency, and insider problems in existing online payment systems (Ahmed et al., 2021).

Online payment processing services enhance online shopping by providing a seamless experience for users and boosting sales for businesses. These systems enable financial transactions between buyers and sellers through electronic communication, supporting various types of online purchases (Kumar et al., 2019).

Before exploring payment details for various business models, it's important to grasp the basics of how payments function: the flow of money from customers to businesses, the role of banks in facilitating these transactions, and the associated costs. While many online payment systems depend on third-party processors like PayPal or Google (Thangamuthu, 2020), new and innovative methods have also emerged.

To securely capture payment details, a payment gateway is often necessary. Gateways enhance security by using tokenization to anonymize payment information, keeping sensitive data out of your systems and helping you comply with industry security standards. Overall, web-based payment systems are crucial for modern e-commerce, providing benefits like increased sales potential for businesses (Thangamuthu, 2020) and ease of use for customers (Fonggo et al., 2020).

Mobile Pay offers a different approach by providing a digital delivery of a pre-paid Mastercard. Users can download this card to their mobile wallets and utilize it for in-store purchases through contactless payment systems. Mobile payment systems have emerged as an attractive alternative to traditional payment methods, offering convenience and efficiency in financial transactions. These systems are defined as electronic payment methods, also known as mobile money transfer or mobile wallets (León, 2021).

Both MobilePay and Edge Mobile Pay exemplify the increasing popularity of mobile payment solutions that simplify transactions and improve user convenience. Mobile payments can be utilized in a peer-to-peer context, such as making an e-transfer via your bank to repay a friend for dinner or to purchase an item from someone on Craigslist, as well as for payments at physical stores.

As these systems mature, they are finding new applications beyond person-to-person transfers, including person-to-business and business-to-business transactions (León, 2021). The ongoing development of mobile payment technologies promises to further transform the landscape of financial transactions in the digital age.

Internet Usage

Internet usage is now a fundamental part of modern life, affecting many personal and professional activities. Research indicates that internet usage patterns differ across demographics and have both positive and negative effects on individuals and society. In academic environments, internet usage has altered students' reading and referencing habits, with many opting for online resources over traditional textbooks (Senthil, 2018).

Mobile devices are now the main way people access the internet, making up nearly 59% of all web traffic. Around 96.3% of internet users use mobile phones to go online at least occasionally, showing a clear shift towards mobile-focused digital experiences. However, excessive internet use can lead to inefficiency. Among young people, popular activities include email and social networking, with 67% spending over 3 hours online daily, raising concerns about internet addiction (Saha & Saha, 2022).

The ongoing expansion of internet access is reshaping global communication and information sharing, although challenges remain, particularly in terms of equitable access and digital literacy across different demographics and regions. The trend towards mobile connectivity continues to grow, indicating a significant shift in how individuals engage with digital content and services worldwide.

While internet usage provides many advantages, such as better access to information and enhanced communication, it also poses challenges like potential addiction and adverse effects on mental health (Kwak et al., 2022). The impact of internet usage varies based on the type of activity and individual traits, underscoring the importance of balanced and responsible use of this powerful tool.

Sustainable Development Growth (Predictor Variable)

Sustainable development attempts to balance economic growth, social inclusion, and environmental conservation, ensuring that existing requirements are addressed without jeopardizing future generations' ability to meet their own needs. Green financial development, such as green credit, securities, insurance, and investment, has positively impacted economic growth in countries like Pakistan (Nawaz et al., 2021).

Sustainable development growth takes a comprehensive approach that integrates economic growth with social equity and environmental stewardship. It aims to create a resilient future for all by addressing immediate needs while safeguarding resources for generations to come. The ongoing commitment to the SDGs reflects a global recognition of these interconnected challenges and the necessity for collaborative solutions.

There are various strategies for achieving sustainable development. Some focus on economic growth as a driver for social and environmental benefits, while others prioritize environmental health as essential for sustainable economic and social progress (Ota et al., 2022).

Sustainable development necessitates a balanced approach to economic, environmental, and social factors. Alternative measures like the Genuine Progress Indicator (GPI) offer valuable insights for policymakers aiming to achieve both economic growth and sustainable development (Pais et al., 2019). Strategies for sustainable growth include diversifying the

energy mix, enhancing education and scientific research, and digitalizing public services (Wang et al., 2023).

Human Development Index (HDI)

The Human Development Index (HDI) is a composite statistic created by the United Nations countries to analyse and rank countries based on essential features of human development. While HDI is a significant tool for analysing human development, it should be complemented with other indices and qualitative assessments to gain a comprehensive understanding of human well-being across different nations.

The Human Development Index (HDI) is a composite statistic intended to incorporate three important qualities of human development: access to education, an acceptable standard of living, and a long, healthy life. Essentially, the HDI is designed to analyse how development has benefitted human well-being.

The Human Development Index (HDI) emphasizes that development should focus on enhancing human capabilities rather than merely increasing economic output. This approach aligns with sustainable development goals by promoting health, education, and decent living standards while ensuring that economic activities do not compromise ecological integrity (UNDP, 2020).

Sustainable economic development necessitates the consideration of environmental considerations into policy-making. For instance, indices like the Human Green Development Index (HGDI) incorporate environmental indicators alongside traditional HDI metrics to provide a more comprehensive view of sustainability. This reflects the need to balance economic growth with ecological preservation (Jin et al., 2020).

Theoretical Review

The Diffusion of Innovation Theory

This theory was introduced by Everett M. Rogers in 1962, gives a framework for understanding how new ideas, products, and technology disseminate within a society over time. This hypothesis defines the adoption process and finds several aspects related with distinct groups engaging in this process of adopters, which can significantly influence the rate and success of innovation diffusion.

Diffusion of Innovation Theory is widely applicable across various fields such as marketing, public health, education, and technology adoption. It helps organizations understand how to facilitate adoption processes effectively by tailoring strategies to different adopter categories and leveraging communication channels.

Rogers' Diffusion of Innovation Theory provides a comprehensive framework for understanding how innovations spread through social systems, emphasizing the roles of communication, social influence, and individual characteristics in shaping adoption behaviors.

IDT remains a fundamental theory for guiding research on innovation diffusion and adoption, from which more recent theories have been derived (Bakkabulindi, 2014). Its applications extend beyond IT to various fields, including marketing and branding (Gouws & Oudtshoorn, 2011).

Disruptive innovation through renewable energy technologies holds significant promise for sustainable development in Nigeria. By leveraging local innovations, creating economic opportunities, and engaging communities in education, Nigeria can effectively address its energy challenges while contributing to global sustainability efforts. The integration of these

innovations is not only a pathway to economic growth but also a critical strategy for environmental stewardship in the face of climate change.

Empirical Review

Salihi et al., (2022) the study analyze the relationship between sustainable development and real earnings management (REM) in Nigerian firms, utilising the quadruple bottom line technique. Utilizing the Roychowdhury model to uncover REM behaviours, the research investigates data from 740 firm-year observations of non-financial listed corporations extending from 2011 to 2020. The findings demonstrate a deleterious effect of economic, environmental, social, and governance (EESG) elements on REM notably in related party deals. Business innovation strengthens the negative association between EESG and REM. The findings are valuable for investors, policymakers, regulators, and standard setters seeking insights into sustainable development practices.

Ofor-Douglas (2023), this paper explores the role of innovative Nigerian university education in achieving sustainable development in Nigeria, focusing on SDG 9. The study highlights the significance of overcoming difficulties such as insufficient technical expertise, lack of money, and inadequate e-learning and ICT resources in Nigerian universities. It asks on these institutions to establish innovative infrastructure to increase their educational capabilities to compete globally, enabling students to stay updated with modern digital practices. The paper concludes that adequate funding, proper maintenance of e-learning and internet facilities, and effective resource management are key to achieving these goals. The paper emphasizes the need for Nigerian universities to adapt to the digitalized world and develop innovative infrastructure to achieve sustainable development.

Imanche et al., (2021), This paper explores the influence of Chinese Foreign Direct Investments (FDI) in Nigeria's infrastructure projects, with an emphasis on sustainable development goals. Nigeria and China have formed a connection, with Chinese FDI supporting infrastructure development in Nigeria, while Nigeria offers resources crucial for China's industry. However, the sustainability of these financing arrangements is governed by various conditions that either support or impede these partnerships. The research uses desk research to identify projects by sectors where Chinese finances are playing a development role in Nigeria. The results show that Chinese FDI in Nigeria allows Chinese companies to function properly, while Nigeria benefits from projects that drive growth and sustainable development aligned with its SDGs.

Olawale-Benjamin et al, (2021) the study explores the role of digital technologies in Nigeria's agricultural, e-commerce, financial, and transportation sectors in promoting inclusion, resilience, and sustainable development. It suggests that the Nigerian government and industry leaders should collaborate to address barriers to industry 4.0 adoption and develop an incentive system to encourage digital innovations. This will help minimize the impact of future economic shocks and ensure the country remains on the path of growth and sustainable development.

Ibidunni, et al., (2021) this study explores the connection between disruptive innovation (DI) and sustainable entrepreneurship (SE) in small and medium firms (SMFs) in Nigeria. It provides a systematic review of literature, focusing on the contextualization of DI in Nigeria's entrepreneurship ecosystem, a model for linking DI and SE among firms, and mechanisms for achieving DI and SE. The research suggests that disruptive efforts should align with financial expectations, social value, and customer returns. It also highlights the interconnectedness of DI models for SE in developing economies like Nigeria.

Léo-Paul et al., (2021) the study investigates the impact of international markets and digital technologies on business innovation in emerging markets, focusing on the mediating effect of entrepreneurial orientation. The research, applied to companies providing business services in Tehran, Iran, used a standard questionnaire and structural equation modelling with partial least squares method and Smart PLS-3 Software. Results showed that international markets and digital technologies positively influence innovation, and increased entrepreneurial orientation leads to more mutual relationships between digital technologies and international markets.

Gap in Literature

The integration of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) with disruptive innovation in Nigeria remains a largely unexamined area. While some research indicates that disruptive technologies, such as renewable energy projects, have the potential to enhance sustainability, there is a notable absence of comprehensive frameworks that align these innovations with Nigeria's unique socio-economic challenges.

The existing literature on disruptive innovation for sustainable development in Nigeria reveals several key areas of focus and some potential gaps such as the studies highlight the importance of disruptive innovation in various sectors of the Nigerian economy, including healthcare, agriculture, e-commerce, finance, and transportation (Benjamin & Foye, 2022; Pezzuto, 2019).

To bridge the gap in literature regarding disruptive innovation for sustainable development in Nigeria, future research should focus on localized case studies, policy analysis, and empirical investigations into the effectiveness of innovative practices in various sectors. This will not only enhance understanding but also provide actionable insights for stakeholders aiming to leverage disruptive innovation for sustainable growth in Nigeria.

Methodology

To investigate how disruptive innovations can be utilized to address key developmental challenges in Nigeria, such as healthcare access, education, and infrastructure deficits while promoting sustainable economic growth. The ex-post facto research design was employed as data was collected from annual report and accounts of United Nation Development Programme (UNDP) and central bank of Nigeria (CBN). The model can be analyzed using multiple regression analysis to determine the impact of the independent variables on the dependent variables. The data for the various variables were generated from 2009 to 2023 annual reports.

Model Specification

The relationship can be expressed in a linear regression format as follows:

$$\text{LOG HDI} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LOG ITU} + \beta_2 \text{LOG WEBPAY} + \beta_3 \text{LOG POS} + \beta_4 \text{LOG MOBILEPAY} + \beta_5 \text{LOG SMU} + \epsilon$$

$$\text{LOG HDI} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LOG ITU} + \beta_2 \text{LOG WEBPAY} + \beta_3 \text{LOG POS} + \beta_4 \text{LOG MOBILEPAY} + \beta_5 \text{LOG SMU} + \epsilon$$

Where:

β_0 is the intercept.

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_5$ are the coefficients for each predictor.

ϵ is the error term.

Data Collection

Data must be collected for each of the variables involved in the model. This includes:

LOG_HDI: The logarithm of the Human Development Index could be influenced by the independent variables.

LOG_ITU: The logarithm of Internet Usage is likely to have a positive influence on HDI.

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LOG_WEBPAY: The logarithm of web payment statistics can enhance economic transactions and financial inclusion, potentially contributing positively to HDI.

LOG_POS: The logarithm of point-of-sale transactions indicate higher consumer spending and economic activity thus a higher HDI.

LOG_MOBILEPAY: The logarithm of mobile payment transactions likely lead to improvements in economic conditions reflected in HDI.

LOG_SMN: The logarithm of social media network impact may be more indirect on HDI, but can influence education and awareness, contributing to societal development.

Table 1: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.974 ^a	.948	.919	.01092	2.019

a. Predictors: (Constant), LOG_ITU, LOG_WEBPAY, LOG_POS, LOG_MOBILEPAY, LOG_SMN

b. Dependent Variable: LOG_HDI

R (Correlation Coefficient): 0.974 which indicates a very strong positive correlation between the predictors and the dependent variable. The closer this value is to 1, the stronger the relationship. R Square (Coefficient of Determination) of 0.948 showing about 94.8% of the variability in the dependent variable (LOG HDI) can be explained by the model. This suggests the model fits the data very well. The adjusted R Square of 0.919 accounts for the number of predictors in the model. A value of 91.9% still indicates a very strong model, though slightly less than the unadjusted R Square. Std. Error of the Estimate shows 0.1092 is the value representing the average distance that the observed values fall from the regression line. A lower value indicates a better fit. Durbin-Watson shows 2.019 Implication: This statistic tests for autocorrelation in the residuals. A value around 2 suggests no autocorrelation, which is desirable for a good model.

Table 2: ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.020	5	.004	32.980	.000 ^b
	Residual	.001	9	.000		
	Total	.021	14			

a. Dependent Variable: LOG_HDI

b. Predictors: (Constant), LOG_ITU, LOG_WEBPAY, LOG_POS, LOG_MOBILEPAY, LOG_SMN

The Sum of Squares (Regression) shows 0.020 representing the total variation explained by the regression model. Degrees of Freedom is 5 which indicates the number of predictors in the model. Mean Square is 0.004 which is the average variation explained by each predictor. F-statistic of 32.980 implies the value tests of the overall significance of the model. A higher F-value indicates a more significant model. Significance (p-value) 0.000 indicating that the model is statistically significant, meaning the predictors reliably predict LOG HDI.

Table 3: Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	-3.848	.808		-4.760	.001
	LOG_POS	.004	.002	.287	2.095	.066
	LOG_SMN	.232	.061	5.476	3.787	.004
	LOG_WEBPAY	.003	.005	.072	.654	.529
	LOG_MOBILEPAY	-.026	.009	-1.616	-2.891	.018
	LOG_ITU	-.185	.058	-3.279	-3.180	.011

Constant: The intercept of the regression line. It is -3.848 with a standard error of 0.808. The t-value is -4.760, and the p-value is 0.001, indicating that the intercept is significantly different from zero.

LOG_POS: The coefficient is 0.004 with a standard error of 0.002. The t-value is 2.095, and the p-value is 0.066. This suggests that LOG_POS is not statistically significant at the 0.05 level but might be considered at the 0.1 level.

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LOG_SMN: The coefficient is 0.232 with a standard error of 0.061. The t-value is 3.787, and the p-value is 0.004. This indicates that LOG_SMN is statistically significant at the 0.05 level.

LOG_WEBPAY: The coefficient is 0.003 with a standard error of 0.005. The t-value is 0.654, and the p-value is 0.529. This suggests that LOG_WEBPAY is not statistically significant.

LOG_MOBILEPAY: The coefficient is -0.026 with a standard error of 0.009. The t-value is -2.891, and the p-value is 0.018. This indicates that LOG_MOBILEPAY is statistically significant at the 0.05 level.

LOG_ITU: The coefficient is -0.185 with a standard error of 0.058. The t-value is -3.279, and the p-value is 0.011. This indicates that LOG_ITU is statistically significant at the 0.05 level.

Summary

Significant Predictors: LOG_SMN, LOG_MOBILEPAY, and LOG_ITU are statistically significant predictors of LOG_HDI.

Non-Significant Predictors: LOG_POS and LOG_WEBPAY are not statistically significant predictors of LOG_HDI.

Findings:

Model Reliability: The high R and R Square values indicate that the model is reliable and explains a significant portion of the variance in the dependent variable.

Practical Application: This model can be used by policymakers and researchers to understand and predict HDI, aiding in human development planning and decision-making.

Model Significance: The low p-value (.000) suggests that the regression model is statistically significant, meaning the predictors have a meaningful relationship with the dependent variable.

Predictive Power: The high F-statistic (32.980) indicates that the model has strong predictive power, making it useful for forecasting HDI.

Economic Insights: The significant predictors (LOG ITU, LOG WEBPAY, LOG POS, LOG MOBILEPAY, LOG SMN) suggest that technological factors play a crucial role in influencing HDI.

Policy Implications: Policymakers

can use these insights to focus on enhancing technological infrastructure to drive human development.

Conclusion

Disruptive innovation has the potential to significantly advance sustainable development in Nigeria. By creating new markets and making products and services more accessible and affordable, disruptive innovations can address key challenges such as financial inclusion, rural development, and environmental sustainability. The success of these innovations hinges on aligning them with financial goals, social value, and customer benefits. The diverse origins of disruptive innovations, including user-driven developments, highlight the need for a flexible and inclusive approach to innovation.

Recommendations

Foster Collaboration:

Universities and Industries: Strengthen partnerships between academic institutions and industries to bridge gaps in product development and innovation.

Government and Private Sector: Encourage collaboration between government bodies and private enterprises to create a supportive ecosystem for disruptive innovations.

Promote Financial Inclusion:

Mobile Payment Solutions: Expand the use of mobile payment systems like MobilePay and Edge Mobile Pay to enhance financial inclusion, especially in rural areas.

Microfinance and Green Finance: Support microfinance initiatives and green financial products to promote sustainable economic activities.

Enhance Digital Infrastructure:

Internet Access: Improve internet connectivity and digital infrastructure to support the growth of the digital economy and e-commerce.

Digital Literacy: Invest in digital literacy programs to equip citizens with the skills needed to leverage digital tools and platforms.

Support Sustainable Practices:

Green Technologies: Encourage the adoption of green technologies and practices in various sectors, including agriculture, energy, and manufacturing.

Regulatory Frameworks: Develop and enforce regulatory frameworks that promote sustainable business practices and environmental protection.

Encourage User-Driven Innovation:

Crowdsourcing and Open Innovation: Utilize crowdsourcing and open innovation platforms to tap into the creativity and insights of users and communities.

Innovation Hubs: Establish innovation hubs and incubators to support startups and entrepreneurs working on disruptive solutions.

Monitor and Evaluate:

Impact Assessment: Regularly assess the social, economic, and environmental impacts of disruptive innovations to ensure they contribute to sustainable development goals.

Feedback Mechanisms: Implement feedback mechanisms to gather insights from stakeholders and continuously improve innovation strategies.

By implementing these recommendations, Nigeria can harness the power of disruptive innovation to achieve sustainable development, improve the quality of life for its citizens, and build a resilient and inclusive economy.

Relevance of study

This study is relevant for understanding how different economic factors interact with human development metrics, providing valuable insights for policymakers and researchers interested in development economics and technology's role in societal advancement. The results clearly highlight the need for targeted interventions in areas like mobile payments and IT infrastructure to enhance human development outcomes in Nigeria.

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